

Visualizing The Strategic Plan of an Organization to Monitor KPIs Using a Dashboard Development Approach. Case Study: Computer Science Faculty of Allameh Tabataba'i University

Hasina Haidari ^{*1}, Hassan Rashidi², Latifeh PourMohammad Bagher³

- 1- Student (Computer Science Faculty – Allameh Tabataba'i University, Tehran, Iran)
Hasina.Haidari18@gmail.com
- 2- Professor (Computer Science Faculty – Allameh Tabataba'i University, Tehran, Iran)
Hrashi@gmail.com
- 3- _Professor (Computer Science Faculty – Allameh Tabataba'i University. Tehran, Iran)
l_pmb@atu.ac.ir

Abstract

This research aimed to identify key performance indicators (KPIs) and enhance the monitoring and decision-making processes within the Faculty of Statistics, Mathematics, and Computer Science at Allameh Tabataba'i University. The study explored the feasibility of visualizing these KPIs through the development of interactive strategic dashboards. Initially, by analyzing the faculty's strategic documents, 11 key performance indicators were identified, including scholarly publications, scientific events, and research projects, which were validated based on the SMART model. Subsequently, interactive dashboards were developed using the powerful Microsoft PowerBI software. These dashboards visually represent the status of each key indicator and enable in-depth data analysis. Dashboards were designed for each academic department (Statistics, Mathematics, and Computer Science) as well as for the entire faculty. The results of this research demonstrate that the use of interactive management dashboards has yielded numerous benefits, including precise and timely monitoring of the faculty's strategic objectives, identification of strengths and weaknesses, facilitation of data-driven decision-making, increased transparency and accountability, and improved efficiency and effectiveness of faculty activities. Overall, this study indicates that the application of modern technologies such as data visualization can significantly contribute to enhancing management and planning in academic environments.

Keywords: Data Visualization, Dashboard, Strategic Plan, Key Performance Indicators, SMART, Usability, Allameh Tabataba'i University

1- INTRODUCTION

In today's data driven era, organizations require powerful tools to analyze vast amounts of data and make informed decisions in order to maintain their competitiveness and achieve their strategic goals. Interactive dashboards, which provide a comprehensive and visual overview of data, have emerged as one such powerful tool. These dashboards assist managers in identifying trends, patterns, and opportunities, ultimately leading to improved organizational

performance. Universities, as educational and research institutions, also leverage these tools to enhance service quality, increase efficiency, monitor their KPIs and achieve their long-term objectives. This research aims to evaluate the role of interactive strategic dashboards in improving the decision-making process within the Faculty of Statistics, Mathematics, and Computer Science at Allameh Tabataba'i University. By utilizing the dashboards developed in this study, the faculty's key performance indicators can be accurately and effectively measured and monitored, enabling data-driven strategic decision-making. This will assist the faculty in achieving its goals and attaining a competitive position in higher education.

This research, with a focus on the faculty's strategic plan, endeavors to initially identify key performance indicators and align them with the SMART goal-setting model. Subsequently, a comprehensive interactive dashboard is designed and implemented using data visualization tools. This dashboard allows faculty managers to gain a comprehensive overview of the faculty's current status, trends, and key performance indicators growth. Furthermore, through in-depth data analysis, the faculty's strengths and weaknesses can be identified, and improvement strategies can be proposed. Ultimately, the findings of this research can serve as a model for other faculties and universities to enhance their decision-making processes and improve the quality of their educational and research services. The subsequent sections of this paper will delve deeper into each of these aspects.

2- LITERATURE REVIEW

In this section, we will first introduce the basic concepts and definitions, followed by a review of the existing literature on this topic, including scholarly articles and theses.

2-1 Basic concepts and definitions

The definitions of the most important concepts related to business intelligence and data visualization required for this study are as follows:

Business Intelligence: Business Intelligence encompasses a range of technologies, applications, and methodologies employed for the collection, integration, analysis, and dissemination of business information. The fundamental objective of BI is to facilitate data-driven decision-making within organizations [1].

Data Visualization: Data visualization involves the utilization of visual representations to explore, comprehend, and communicate data. It is intimately connected to the disciplines of information visualization, information graphics, scientific visualization, and statistical graphics. Business intelligence systems incorporate a diverse array of data displays and interactive methods, including reports (static and dynamic), digital dashboards, and sophisticated visual analytics tools [1].

Strategic Planning: A strategic plan constitutes a strategic document formulated by organizations that delineates goals, actions, and strategies to attain long-term objectives and establish the organization's overall direction. This plan is typically developed at a macro level for one or more years and provides a detailed specification of the organization's long-term goals [2].

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs): A KPI is a measurable value that demonstrates how effectively a company is achieving key business objectives. Organizations use these metrics to evaluate their success in meeting their goals [3].

Management Dashboard: A management dashboard is a visual tool that helps managers and management teams within an organization to graphically display important information and key performance indicators. The advantage of using management dashboards in organizations is that by providing key information in real-time and interactively, it enables the rapid and accurate monitoring and tracking of organizational performance [4].

Decision-making Process: Decision-making is a process in which one of two or more alternatives is selected to achieve one or more objectives. Managerial decision-making is synonymous with the entire management process [1].

SMART Model: The SMART model in key performance indicators is a systematic approach used to define and set performance metrics. SMART is an acronym for Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound [5].

Usability: Usability in management dashboards refers to the simplicity and user-friendliness of the dashboard's features and design. This important feature facilitates access to information and performance indicators, reduces training time and costs, and minimizes the need for technical skills. Through a simple user interface and easy access to information, users can quickly and accurately conduct analyses and make strategic decisions [6].

ETL Process: ETL stands for Extract, Transform, and Load. It is a process used when building data warehouses. It involves collecting data from one or more sources, cleaning and transforming the data, and finally loading it into the data warehouse [1].

Data Warehouse: A data warehouse is a centralized repository for collecting, storing, and managing organizational data. This system collects data from various sources and stores it in a unified and structured manner in a centralized location [1].

2-2- Related Researches

Numerous studies have been conducted on the visualization of key performance indicators (KPIs) using dashboard approaches in organizations. Frady et al., in their paper titled "Decision Support in Engineering Design Based on Shared Dashboards: Integrating Business and BI Techniques," examined the analysis of data and the creation of actionable and profitable information for project monitoring and decision-making. The study employed an information technology architecture to implement the approach, combining three business process modules (involving multiple actors and data sources). Key findings include the extraction of KPIs from various data sources and their visualization using business intelligence techniques, particularly data visualization and dashboard techniques. However, the study lacked a specific approach for selecting KPIs and did not compare different visualization tools [7].

Kulichkov and Shchobotinov (2019), in their paper titled "Using Business Intelligence Tools for Visualizing KPIs of a Telecommunications Company," investigated the practical application of visual analytics tools for decision-making, focusing on visualizing large volumes of data using business intelligence tools. They visualized KPIs as a tool for supporting managerial decisions and building business models in technology companies using visual

models. They concluded that visualizing KPIs significantly impacts the measurement of performance efficiency and the evaluation of the effectiveness of developing selected activities. A limitation of this study is the lack of consideration for design principles in dashboard development [8].

In another study, Zdonk (2020), focusing on "Visualizing Metrics Using an Interactive Dashboard," designed specific dashboards to display project metrics aimed at increasing their understandability, usability, and customization. The study used previous research to identify dashboard design principles and then created a real-world project management dashboard to investigate technical challenges and solutions for creating a useful tool to support project team work. The study concluded that important factors for dashboard comprehensibility include an appropriate number of charts, selecting suitable charts based on data and required actions, and color design considering color-impaired users. Additionally, the dashboard should provide usability (scannability) for users, and time elements and filtering should be added. For customization, the dashboard should display project metrics based on the project team's tasks. A limitation of this study is the lack of a specific method for selecting project metrics [9].

Pila (2017), in their thesis titled "Analysis of Key Performance Indicators and Dashboard Visualization in a Logistics Company," focused on identifying and visualizing key performance indicators in the logistics sector to optimize processes. The research employed performance measurement and data visualization theories to create operational models and dashboard planning. The study identified suitable performance indicators for various processes and user needs, and developed operational and planning dashboard models adaptable to the specific company. By utilizing data visualization, performance measurement was improved, and the sharing of appropriate indicators with specific user groups was facilitated [10].

Ramprasad (2019), in their research titled "Selection and Visualization of Key Performance Indicators in Product Development," emphasized the importance of performance measurement and the use of KPIs in various industries. This research explored how KPIs can be leveraged in product development and how dashboards can be used as tools for visualizing and linking them to organizational strategy and performance. The study identified key factors in selecting and visualizing KPIs for communication with stakeholders at various levels of the organization. Furthermore, a framework for dashboard development was presented based on five key factors, along with guidelines for the successful development and acceptance of effective dashboards using the technology acceptance model. The thesis concluded that by using KPIs and dashboards, organizations can establish effective communication with stakeholders and develop, adopt, and implement effective dashboards [11].

Poll (2022), in their thesis titled "Visualizing Company Performance Using Dashboards," developed management dashboards for Peddler, a startup selling local store products through an online platform. The research involved a systematic literature review and the use of various methods and tools for data analysis to develop suitable dashboards. Additionally, through multiple interviews, accurate information about the company was collected, and appropriate performance indicators were provided for evaluation. The use of various dashboards in this research led to significant results. Some of the results included allocating appropriate timeframes to postal codes, analyzing the performance of different cities and regions, and examining the performance of stores and couriers. However, one of the limitations of this research was the lack of attention to usability principles in dashboard development, resulting in low usability [12].

Marella's 2023 thesis titled "Digitalization of Key Performance Indicators for Quality" underscores the significance of KPIs in business processes and the utilization of data analysis and visualization for informed decision-making. The paper employs various software tools to analyze data and create diverse visualizations, such as line charts, bar charts, Pareto charts, and scatter plots. Additionally, the study examines different software tools for data visualization and offers recommendations in this area. However, one limitation of this study is the absence of a clear and systematic method for selecting KPIs within the case study [13].

3- METHODOLOGY

In this research, key performance indicators (KPIs) will be identified based on the objectives outlined in the faculty's strategic plan and using the SMART framework. Data required for these KPIs will be collected from various sources, such as university information systems and surveys. After data extraction and transformation, the data will be loaded into a cloud-based data warehouse. Finally, using this data, management dashboards will be designed and implemented to enable managers to make informed decisions and continuously monitor the faculty's performance. Figure 1 provides an overview of the research process.

Figure 1. Research Phases

Stage 1: Selecting Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) based on the SMART Model: The SMART model, a well-known framework for goal setting, will be used to identify suitable KPIs. SMART stands for Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound.

Stage 2: Extracting Required Data Aligned with KPIs from the Faculty's Strategic Plan: Data extraction is the initial phase of the ETL (Extract, Transform, Load) process. For this research, the faculty's strategic plan will be analyzed to gather necessary data. The required data will be stored in suitable formats such as Word and Excel files.

Stage 3: Data Transformation: Data transformation is a critical step in the ETL process. This stage involves cleaning, aggregating, filtering, deriving, enriching, and removing duplicate raw data before processing and analysis.

Stage 4: Data Loading: After data transformation, the extracted and refined data from various sources will be loaded into the data warehouse. In this stage, data is loaded into the data warehouse without any changes from the intermediate environment. Different architectures (such as three-tier, two-tier, independent data marts, data mart bus architecture, hub and spoke, centralized, and federated) can be used for data warehouse design. Based on organizational needs and data processing volume, a centralized architecture will be designed and the data warehouse will be hosted on Google Sheets.

Stage 5: Reviewing and Studying Interaction Design Principles: Interaction design principles play a crucial role in dashboards and can significantly impact user experience and organizational efficiency. An interactive dashboard allows users to actively engage with organizational data and make better decisions. Therefore, in this stage, dashboard design principles will be examined for application in the subsequent dashboard development stage.

Stage 6: Designing Management Dashboards for the Organization Considering Interaction Design Principles: In this stage, data previously extracted, transformed, and loaded into the data warehouse will be visualized using Power BI, a data visualization tool ranked as the top data visualization tool in 2023 by Forbes. The data visualized in this dashboard will be the KPIs from the faculty's strategic plan.

3-1 Data

This research utilizes data obtained from the strategic plan of the Department of Statistics, Mathematics, and Computer Science at Allameh Tabataba'i University. The dataset encompasses both quantitative and qualitative information pertaining to the department's key performance indicators over a three-year period (2023, 2022, and 2024). By analyzing this data, it is possible to examine trends in the indicators and identify the department's strengths and weaknesses."

3-2 Method

SMART Model: To evaluate key performance indicators, the SMART model was employed. This model assists in selecting and examining specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound indicators. The SMART model is a framework for setting objectives, and in this research, it was applied to assess the faculty's key performance indicators. This model helps ensure that the selected indicators for evaluation are specific, measurable, achievable, aligned with the faculty's overall objectives, and have a defined timeline. By utilizing this model, we can more accurately evaluate the faculty's progress towards achieving its strategic goals.

3-3 Tools:

- 1- **Google Sheets** (for data loading into the dashboard): A free, web-based tool for creating, editing, and sharing spreadsheets. It serves as an alternative to Microsoft Excel, allowing users to access and analyze data using a web browser. Key features of Google Sheets include:
 1. Creating and editing spreadsheets: Users can create new spreadsheets, input and edit data, utilize formulas and functions for calculations, generate charts and graphs, and more.
 2. Real-time collaboration: Multiple users can simultaneously work on a spreadsheet and view changes instantly.
 3. Cloud storage: Spreadsheets are automatically saved to the cloud, allowing access from anywhere.
 4. Offline access: The Google Sheets app provides offline access to spreadsheets.
 5. Free: Google Sheets is entirely free, requiring no paid subscription.

- 2- **Microsoft Power BI** (for final dashboard development): A widely used tool for data analysis and visualization provided by Microsoft. It can collect data from various sources such as databases, Excel files, web services, and more, allowing users to analyze data and visualize it as charts and tables using a simple graphical user interface. This tool also supports publishing analytical reports online and creating analytical dashboards. Additionally, users can quickly analyze their data and create high-quality, visually appealing charts. Another advantage is its ability to connect with other Microsoft tools like Excel and SharePoint, enabling users to quickly and easily utilize their data in various areas such as analysis, visualization, and data presentation [14].

4- RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the results obtained from data analysis are presented in detail, followed by an interpretation and discussion of these findings.

4-1 Case study

Allameh Tabataba'i University is one of the most prestigious universities in Iran and the region, recognized as the country's sole specialized institution for humanities and social sciences. While its foundations date back 60 years, the university was officially established in 1984, following the Islamic Revolution, to address the growing need for a specialized institution in the humanities and social sciences. It was formed by merging various independent educational institutions, including universities, faculties, research centers, and institutes, that had been established since 1958.

The Faculty of Statistics, Mathematics, and Computer Science of Allameh Tabataba'i University comprises the departments of Statistics, Financial Mathematics, and Computer Science. Its initial activities began in 1989 with the approval to establish a statistics program within the Faculty of Economics. In 1997, the first Master's program in Economic and Social Statistics was launched, followed by programs in Financial Mathematics and Computer Science in subsequent years. The faculty officially commenced its operations as an independent entity in 2013 [15].

4-2 Structure of Computer Science Faculty Strategic Plan

The operational program of this faculty, encompassing a diverse set of targeted activities, outlines a roadmap for enhancing the academic, research, and educational standards of the faculty. This program encompasses various activities such as organizing academic conferences and seminars, publishing books, conducting training workshops, fostering academic leadership among faculty members, and collaborating with other faculties and scientific centers. These activities are designed to enhance the knowledge and skills of faculty members and students, promote the production and dissemination of knowledge in the humanities, and establish connections with the scientific community and the general public" [15].

4-3 Validation of KPIs based on SMART Model

In this research, given the significance of selecting appropriate key performance indicators (KPIs) to evaluate faculty performance aligned with the strategic plan, the SMART model was employed as a comprehensive framework. To identify these KPIs, a previous study (Rashidi et al., 2023) conducted at the same university on a similar topic was consulted. This study extracted a set of KPIs based on the university's strategic plan. Considering the validity and alignment of the extracted KPIs with the university's conditions and objectives, this research also adopted these KPIs as key performance indicators at the faculty level of Statistics, Mathematics, and Computer Science, which are as follows:

- Book publications
- Domestic article publications
- International article publications
- Promotional chair sessions
- Problem-solving workshops
- Implementation of educational projects
- Startup establishment
- Organization of promotional chair sessions, workshops, and conferences
- Other programs [16].

In this study, considering the nature and level of research activities, the KPIs "intra-faculty research projects," "intra-university research projects," and "extra-university research projects" were considered as replacements for the general indicator "other programs." This change was made for reasons such as greater measurement accuracy, reflecting existing realities, and facilitating data analysis. The final KPIs with their definitions are presented in Table 3.

Table 1. KPIs of Faculty

No	KPIs	Definition
۱	Book publications	Production and publication of a comprehensive written work in the relevant field.
۲	Domestic article publications	Publication of research articles in domestic scientific journals.
۳	International article publications	Publication of research articles in international scientific journals.
۴	Promotional chair sessions	Organizing meetings and discussions on scientific and research topics to promote knowledge.
۵	Problem-solving workshops	Holding specialized meetings to analyze and solve problems in various fields.
۶	Implementation of educational projects	Implementing educational and research programs to enhance the academic level of students and faculty.

۷	Startup establishment	Establishing startups and knowledge-based companies to commercialize innovative ideas.
۸	Organization of promotional chair sessions, workshops, and conferences	Organizing various scientific and research events to promote knowledge and foster interactions among researchers.
۹	Intra-faculty research projects	Implementing research projects within the faculty using internal resources.
۱۰	Intra-university research projects	Implementing research projects at the university level in collaboration with other faculties and research centers.
۱۱	Extra-university research projects	Implementing research projects in collaboration with external institutions and organizations.

The SMART model is a robust framework for setting and assessing goals [17]. To verify the alignment of the chosen indicators with this model, Table 2 was employed. This table facilitates a rigorous and clear validation of each indicator across the model's five fundamental dimensions.

Table 2. Validation of KPIs according to SMART model

KPI(s)	Specific	Measurable	Achievable	Relevant	Time-bound
Book publications	refers to the production and publication of a complete written work.	The number of published books is countable.	This is achievable given the available resources and support.	This is important for enhancing the academic reputation of both the author and the faculty.	A specific timeline can be set for the publication of each book.
Domestic article publications	refers to the publication of articles in domestic journals.	The number of articles published in domestic journals is countable.	This is achievable considering the research activities of the faculty members.	This is important for improving the academic level of the faculty and disseminating research findings.	A specific timeline can be set for the publication of articles.
International article publications	refers to the publication of articles in international journals.	The number of articles published in international journals is countable.	This requires more effort and high-quality research.	This is crucial for enhancing the faculty's international ranking and the visibility of its researchers.	A specific timeline can be set for the publication of articles in international journals.
Promotional chair sessions	refers to holding lectures, discussions, and exchanges of ideas.	The number of meetings held and the number of participants are countable.	This is achievable given the available human resources and facilities.	This is important for promoting knowledge and fostering interaction among researchers.	The number of meetings and their schedules can be determined.
Problem-solving workshops	refers to holding specialized meetings to solve problems.	The number of meetings held and the number of participants are countable.	This is achievable considering the identified problems and the availability of experts.	This is important for improving the faculty's performance and addressing challenges.	The time of meetings and the topics to be discussed can be determined.

Implementation of educational projects	refers to the implementation of educational programs.	The number of training courses conducted, the number of participants, and the number of training hours are measurable.	This is achievable given the educational needs and available resources.	This is important for enhancing the academic level of students and faculty members.	The start and end times for each training program can be determined.
Startup establishment	refers to the establishment of startups.	The number of startups created and the amount of investment attracted are measurable.	This requires financial support and appropriate facilities.	This is important for commercializing innovative ideas and generating revenue for the faculty.	A specific timeline can be set for the launch of each startup.
Organization of promotional chair sessions, workshops, and conferences	refers to organizing various scientific events.	The number of events held, the number of participants, and the topics discussed are measurable.	This is achievable given the available resources and facilities	This is important for promoting knowledge and fostering interaction among researchers.	An annual events calendar can be established.
intra-faculty research projects	refers to the implementation of research projects within the faculty.	The number of projects implemented, the budget spent, and the results achieved are measurable.	This is achievable given the faculty's internal resources.	This is important for strengthening both fundamental and applied research within the faculty.	The start and end times for each project can be determined.
Intra-university research projects	refers to the implementation of research projects at the university level.	The number of projects implemented, the budget spent, and the results achieved are measurable.	This requires collaboration with other faculties and research centers.	This is important for strengthening interdisciplinary collaborations and enhancing the level of research at the university.	The start and end times for each project can be determined.
Extra-university research projects	refers to the implementation of research projects in collaboration with external institutions.	The number of projects implemented, the budget spent, and the results achieved are measurable	This requires connections with institutions outside the university and attracting external funding.	This is important for establishing connections with industry and society and enhancing the university's reputation.	The start and end times for each project can be determined.

As seen in the table, all selected indicators align with the various dimensions of the SMART model. This indicates that the indicators are well-defined and can be used for accurate performance evaluation.

4-4 ETL Process

To measure the faculty's progress in achieving the strategic plan of the university and the faculty's operational plan, the required data was extracted from Word and Excel files containing the faculty's operational plan. This data

included information about the faculty's activities centered around key performance indicators (Table 1), activity executors, activity timeline, and so on. Initially, the data was extracted from Word and Excel files, and after data cleaning and removal of duplicates, it was integrated into a unified database (Google Sheets).

4-5 Interactive Design Principles

Interactive dashboard design, as a powerful tool for data analysis and decision-making, holds significant importance. For an interactive dashboard to function effectively and convey information efficiently to users, adhering to specific principles is essential. Table 3 presents the most important principles of interactive dashboard design in terms of usability, outlined in bullet points along with definitions and examples [18].

Table 3. Most Important Interaction Design Principles

Principle	Meaning	Example
Simplicity and fluency	The dashboard should have a simple, clean, and uncluttered design. Visual elements should be chosen so that information is easily understandable.	Use of appropriate colors, legible fonts, and a well-organized layout of elements on the page.
Focus on the goal	The dashboard should have a clear purpose and answer specific questions. The information presented should be relevant to the users' needs.	The dashboard should focus specifically on key performance indicators (KPIs) in an organization.
High interactivity	The dashboard should allow users to easily interact with the data. This includes filtering, sorting, zooming, and panning the data.	The ability to filter data based on date and other important parameters should be available.
Alignment with user cognition	Dashboard design should be based on an understanding of users and how they interact with information. Familiar terms and symbols should be used.	Use bar charts to show comparisons between groups, as this type of chart is familiar and understandable to users.
Compatibility with various devices	The dashboard should display well and be usable on various devices such as desktop, tablet, and mobile.	Design the dashboard using responsive frameworks that automatically adapt to screen size.
Providing information at a glance	The most important information should be conveyed to the user at first glance. Use charts and key performance indicators to display information quickly and easily.	Display the most important information in a large, prominent box at the top of the dashboard.
Meaningful use of colors	Colors should be used meaningfully and to convey specific information. Use a harmonious and distinguishable color palette.	Use the color red to indicate a decrease in growth and green to indicate an increase in growth.
Automatic updates	The dashboard should update automatically so that users always have access to the latest information.	Connect the dashboard to a database and schedule automatic updates at specified intervals.

4-6 Dashboard Development Process

The development process stages should progress from requirements elicitation, where dashboards are built to understand informational needs and how to present them, to dashboard maintenance, where maintenance and corrective support activities are performed. An overview of the stages is presented in Figure 4

Figure 2 – Dashboard Development Process Phases

Requirements Elicitation:

The goal of this stage is to gather high-level expectations for the dashboard and create initial content designs. Dashboard designers should identify stakeholders, information providers, and dashboard users within the organization by conducting interviews. The outcome of this stage is an information model for the dashboard's indicators and a preliminary visual content design.

Dashboard Type Selection:

The goal of this stage is to find the appropriate technology for dashboard implementation. The outcome of this stage is the first dashboard prototype as a proof of concept for the technology.

Dashboard Design:

Depending on the selected technology, designers must iteratively design and evaluate the dashboard. We recommend the concept of a minimum viable product (MVP) and the build-measure-learn approach for this stage. This stage should conclude with an operational dashboard that meets the initial requirements.

Impact Assessment:

After implementing the dashboard, designers should observe its impact on the organization. For this purpose, organizational learning theory by Goodman and Dean is recommended. A successful dashboard in this regard will show signs of influencing company performance, which will be evident in dashboard indicators/metrics after introducing changes.

Dashboard Maintenance:

The final stage is dashboard maintenance, where the designer or a dedicated person monitors the operational dashboard and ensures it displays the required information. The designer must also be involved in updating the dashboard as company goals or data sources change over time. The design and maintenance of dashboards depend on the chosen technology, so designers should assess the organization's needs and carefully select the technology. [19]

4-7 KPIs Interactive Dashboard

To better understand how this dashboard works, we will now examine images of its key pages. These images visually demonstrate how the dashboard transforms complex data into understandable and actionable information. Figure 3 shows an image of the dashboard's homepage where, at this stage, the user selects the desired dashboard based on their needs.

Figure 3. The First Page of Dashboard

Figure-4 presents a view of the dashboard's homepage, where the entire operational program of the faculty is visualized. The diverse charts on this page display information such as: the increase or decrease in growth of 11 key performance indicators of the faculty, the growth trend of these indicators over the past three years, the total number of faculty activities, the number of activities to achieve strategic visions and goals by indicator, the distribution of activities by executors (faculty members), the distribution of activities by seasons, and the type of activity execution (individual or group)

Figure 4. Main Page of Dashboard (Strategic Information about faculty)

Some of the important features of this dashboard page (Figure-4), according to the dashboard design principles mentioned in Table 3, are as follows:

1. Ability to filter and search data based on year, indicator, strategic aspect, goal, activity executor, and activity execution time (principle of high interactivity);
2. Use of specific charts for key performance indicators to show the increase or decrease in growth of each indicator using meaningful colors (principle of using colors meaningfully, green color to show growth increase and red color to show growth decrease);
3. Overall categorization of key performance indicators and use of card charts to display the number of activities in each indicator (principle of focusing on the goal);
4. Use of line charts to show the growth trend of indicators over different years (principle of alignment with user cognition);
5. Use of various charts such as bar charts, pie charts, line charts, stacked bar charts, card charts, donut charts, etc., based on the information (principle of alignment with user cognition);
6. Use of tooltips (brief guides in software) for each chart for greater clarity for the user (principle of simplicity and fluency);
7. Use of relevant and meaningful colors to display data (different color tones to indicate the quantity of a value (principle of using colors meaningfully));
8. Ability for the user to easily navigate between different dashboard pages (existence of buttons to go to other pages (principle of high interactivity));
9. Highlighting important and essential information and prioritizing their charts based on arrangement and font size (principle of presenting information at a glance);
10. Ability for the user to interact with each part of the charts in the dashboard (principle of high interactivity).

Figure 5 shows an example of the interactive feature of the dashboard. By clicking on the second column (second indicator: publishing internal articles), the chart (number of activities based on key performance indicators) changes all the charts on the dashboard page based on this data point (the second key performance indicator of the faculty), and information related to this indicator, such as the number of activities in this indicator, executors of activities, activity time, and more, are highlighted and displayed.

Figure 5. Interactivity of Dashboard

The main dashboard page, displayed in Figure 4, provides a comprehensive overview of the entire faculty's status. This page is intended to be the starting point for users and provides quick access to important information. The structure and visual elements present on this page serve as a template for other dashboard pages, each of which is designed specifically for individual groups (statistics, mathematics, and computer science). While maintaining overall consistency, these pages display the required information for each group in a customized manner.

5- CONCLUSION

The results of this research, focusing on a case study of the Faculty of Statistics, Mathematics, and Computer Science at Allameh Tabataba'i University, demonstrate that interactive dashboards, as a powerful tool, can play a significant role in improving the decision-making process in academic environments. By providing a visual overview of various faculty data, including key performance indicators and their growth trends, activities carried out to achieve strategic goals and visions, the level of faculty member activity, strengths and weaknesses of group and faculty activities, these dashboards enable organizational managers and decision-makers (in this research, the university) to quickly identify trends and hidden patterns in the data. For example, by using a dashboard, it is easy to compare the performance of executors in various activities, identify the strengths and weaknesses of strategic planning, and consequently, make better decisions to improve the quality of the faculty. In addition, interactive dashboards, by reducing data analysis time and increasing decision-making accuracy, help faculty managers to quickly respond to environmental changes and take advantage of new opportunities. For instance, using a dashboard, it is easy to examine the trend of increasing or decreasing growth of key performance indicators and, as a result, plan better to achieve future strategic visions. Furthermore, dashboards, by providing a common language for communication between faculty members, managers, and other stakeholders, help improve collaboration and coordination within the faculty. By using a dashboard, all faculty members can refer to a single, reliable source for the information they need, and as a result, make joint and data-driven decisions. In conclusion, the results of this research show that interactive dashboards can be used as a strategic tool to improve the performance of faculties and universities. By investing in the development and implementation of these tools, it is possible to increase efficiency, improve the quality of education and research, and ultimately enhance the university's position at the national and international levels.

6- REFERENCES

- [1]. Sharda, R., Delen, D. and Turban, E. (2018) Business Intelligence, Analytics, and Data Science: A Managerial Perspective. Pearson, New York.
- [2]. Strategic Plan of Allameh Tabataba'i University, Accessible on: <http://surl.li/bsjzvd>
- [3]. Bernard, M. (2012) Key Performance Indicators: The 75 Measures Every Manager Needs to Know, Pearson,
- [4]. Few, S. (2006) Information Dashboard Design, O'Reilly, Mexico
- [5]. University of California. (2017). SMART Goals: A How to Guide
- [6]. Preece, J., (Author), Sharp, H., Rogers, Y. (2015) Interaction Design: Beyond Human Computer Interaction. John Wiley & Sons Inc
- [7]. Fradi, A., Bircogne, M., Boch-Mauchand, M., Louhichi, B. (2017): Decision-Making Support in Engineering Design Based on Collaborative Dashboards: Integration of Business Intelligence Techniques, Smart Innovation Conference
- [8]. Kolychev, V.D., Shebotinov, A.A. (2019): Application of Business Intelligence instrumental tools for visualization of key performance indicators of an enterprise in telecommunications, National research nuclear university, Moscow
- [9]. ZDONEK, I. (2020): Project Indicators Visualization Using an Interactive Dashboard, Silesian University of Technology, Poland.
- [10]. Piela, J. (2017): Key Performance Indicator Analysis and Dashboard Visualization In A Logistics Company, Lappeenranta University Of Technology, Finland

- [11]. RAMPRASAD, V. (2019): Selection and Visualization of Key Performance Indicators in Product Development, Chalmers University of Technology, Gothenburg, Sweden
- [12]. Pol. S.V.D. (2022): The visualization of efficiency and performance with the use of dashboards, University of Twente, Netherlands.
- [13]. Marella, G. (2023): Digitalization of Quality Key Performance Indicators, Technische Hochschule University, Germany.
- [14]. Microsoft PowerBI formal website, Accessible on: <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/power-bi/>
- [15]. Allameh Tabataba'i website, Accessible on: <https://atu.ac.ir/>
- [16]. Rashidi, H, Khorsandi, M., Shams, F. (1403). A budget optimization modeling for strategic plan Universities - A case study in Allameh Tabatabai University.
- [17]. University of California. (2017) SMART Goals: A How to Guide, Performance Appraisal Planning
- [18]. Martins, N., Brando, D. (2022): Design Principles in the development of Dashboard for business management.
- [19]. Staron, M. (2015): Dashboard development guide - How to build sustainable and useful dashboards to support software development and maintenance, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, University of Gothenburg, Sweden